

Resolution of Co-ordinated Inorganic Compounds into Optical Isomers. Part II. Resolution of Triethylenediaminozinc Chloride and Sulphate.

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The resolution of triethylenediaminocadmium salts into optical isomers has been described in Part I of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 228). We have been able to resolve triethylenediaminozinc chloride and sulphate into optical isomers and isolate the *dextro* compounds in the solid state. As in the case of the triethylenediaminocadmium salts reagents like *d*-tartaric acid, *d*-camphor sulphonic acid, *d*-bromocamphor sulphonic acid, *d*-ammonium tartrate were at first tried, but all these reagents failed to resolve the zinc salts. Success was only achieved with *d*-sodiocamphor nitronate, as in the case of the cadmium salts. The *laevo* variety however, could not be isolated in the solid state though a *laevo*-rotatory solution was obtained by using nitrocamphor itself instead of the *d*-sodio salt. It is to be observed that sodiocamphor nitronate is *dextro*-rotatory whereas nitrocamphor itself is *laevo*-rotatory. Using the sodio salt, the *d*-components both in the case of the cadmium and zinc salts, were obtained in solutions from which acetone precipitated the *dextro* compounds in the solid state.

Using free nitrocamphor for the *laevo*-component the hydroxide of the co-ordinated zinc or cadmium salt was first prepared and combined with nitrocamphor and the resultant salt was fractionally crystallised. In the case of cadmium, the nitronate decomposed and could not be obtained in the pure state. In the case of the zinc salt, however, a *laevo*-rotatory camphor nitronate was obtained in the pure state which on fractional crystallisation yielded a *laevo* compound with a maximum *laevo*-rotation. This compound was decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid when the nitrocamphor separated out in the free state and filtered off and the solution was found to remain *laevo*-rotatory. Acetone or other

organic solvents, however, failed to precipitate the *laevo*-compound in the solid state. The solution, unlike nitrocamphor, soon racemised within a few hours. Details have been given in the experimental.

Unlike cadmium salts, the *d*-bromide and *d*-iodide, which were obtained in solution, were not obtained in the solid state as acetone failed to precipitate them. The compositions and rotations of the tartrate, camphor sulphonate and bromocamphor sulphonate have been incorporated.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Triethylenediaminozinc tartrate.—A concentrated solution of triethylenediaminozinc chloride (3 g.) was triturated with silver tartrate (3 g.) prepared from a concentrated solution of Rochelle salt by precipitation with a concentrated solution of silver nitrate, washing with water and drying in a desiccator covered with black paper. The residue of silver chloride was repeatedly extracted with hot water. The extract was filtered and evaporated in vacuum. Various fractions of crystals were dried and all gave a constant nitrogen content. [Found: N, 19.01; Zn, 14.2. $(\text{Zn En}_3) \text{C}_4\text{H}_4\text{O}_6, 3 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 18.79; Zn, 14.5 per cent). Rotations of these substances were measured in a 2 dcm. tube and after four crystallisations the value of $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ for the first and the last fractions were $+17.4^\circ$ and $+18.1^\circ$ respectively. The values of α_D being $+1.74^\circ$ and $+1.81^\circ$ respectively with a 5% solution. This difference is not greater than the probable experimental error. The solutions showed no muta-rotation, for the rotations were found to be exactly the same even after 24 hours. The tartrate was converted to the corresponding chloride by means of barium chloride but in each case the resulting solution was inactive.

d-Triethylenediaminozinccamphor sulphonate.—To 200 C.c. of a solution of silver nitrate (15 g.) just sufficient caustic soda was added to precipitate all the silver as oxide; this was washed with distilled water until free from alkali salts, filtered and the moist precipitate warmed with 150 c.c. of a solution of *d*-camphor sulphonic acid (20.5 g.). When the dissolution of the oxide was complete, the filtered solution was neutral to litmus. To a concentrated solution of recrystallised triethylenediaminozinc chloride (5 g.) the silver *d*-camphor sulphonate solution was added until the addition of one drop

more caused no further silver chloride to be precipitated. The solution was filtered, evaporated in vacuum and crystallised. It was recrystallised twice from water. [Found: N, 12; Zn, 8.80. $(\text{ZnEn}_3)(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_4\text{S})_2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 11.5; Zn, 8.96 per cent.]. It was then subjected to fractional crystallisation. The rotations of the different fractions were measured in a 2 dm. tube. After four crystallisations the values of the $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ for the first fraction and the last fraction were $+16.5^\circ$ and $+18.1^\circ$ respectively the values of α_D being $+1.65^\circ$ and $+1.81^\circ$ respectively with a 5% solution. The solutions showed no muta-rotation as their rotations did not change even on keeping them for 24 hours. On acidifying a concentrated solution of any of these fractions with hydrochloric acid and adding excess of acetone, the complex zinc chloride precipitated was found to be inactive.

d-Triethylenediaminozincbromocamphor sulphonate.—A solution of the silver salt of *d*-bromocamphor sulphonic acid was prepared in the same way as the silver salt of *d*-camphor sulphonic acid by dissolving silver oxide in a warm solution of *d*-bromocamphor sulphonic acid till a solution neutral to litmus was obtained. To a solution of triethylenediaminozinc chloride (5 g.) in water, the silver bromocamphor sulphonate solution, thus prepared, was added till the addition of one drop more caused no further precipitation of silver chloride. The solution was filtered and the residue of silver chloride was washed with hot water, filtrate evaporated in vacuum and fractionally crystallised and the different fractions purified by further crystallisations. Each of these fractions gave a constant nitrogen content. [Found: N, 9.02; Zn, 6.5. $(\text{ZnEn}_3)(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{BrSO}_4)_2, 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 8.8; Zn, 6.8 per cent].

Rotations of the different fractions were observed in a 2 dm. tube. The values of $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ for the first and the last fractions were 42° and 41° respectively with a 5% solution. On acidifying a concentrated solution of any of these fractions in water with hydrochloric acid and adding acetone in excess the complex zinc chloride was precipitated which was found to be quite inactive.

d-Triethylenediaminocamphor nitronate.—To a solution of triethylenediaminozinc chloride (6 g.) in water (20 c.c.) was added a solution of *d*-sodiocamphor nitronate (6 g.) in water (15 c.c.) and the mixture well shaken. No precipitate appeared. The solution was evaporated in vacuum and three crops of crystals collected, The first

fraction was recrystallised from water when it appeared as colourless silky needles. This was completely free from chlorine. [Found: N, 16.91; Zn, 9.45; $(\text{ZnEn}_3)(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 16.6; Zn, 9.66 per cent].

Rotation of this substance was measured in a 2 dcm. tube and the value of the $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ was found to be $+16^\circ$ the value of α_D being $+9.6^\circ$ with a 3% solution and this rotation did not change on keeping it for 24 hours. The second and the third fractions on further purifications by crystallisation were found to have identical chemical composition and their specific rotations were $+116.6^\circ$ and $+80.4^\circ$ respectively under identical conditions, the actual rotations being $+7.0^\circ$ and $+4.82^\circ$ respectively with a 3% solution.

d-Triethylenediaminozinc chloride.—*d-Triethylenediaminozinc-camphor nitronate* (2 g.) (first fraction) was dissolved in the least quantity of water, and to the clear solution dilute hydrochloric acid was added drop by drop and shaken till all the nitrocamphor had precipitated out. The clear solution was filtered and the residue washed with a small quantity of water. To the filtrate excess of acetone was added when a perfectly white crystalline substance precipitated out which was allowed to settle. The supernatant liquid was then decanted off and the precipitate washed several times with acetone to remove all traces of the acid and any free nitrocamphor. The residue was quickly dried underneath a fan between filter papers. [Found: N, 26.62; Cl, 22.38; Zn, 20.40. $(\text{ZnEn}_3)\text{Cl}_2$ requires N, 26.58; Cl, 22.4; Zn, 20.57 per cent].

0.0398 G. of the substance was dissolved in 15 c.c. of water and a tube was completely filled with the solution (about 10 c.c.) when the rotation was found to be $+0.5^\circ$ which makes $[\alpha]_D^{25} = 94.2^\circ$ and $[M] = +297.6^\circ$.

The activity of the solution rapidly diminished on keeping and almost completely vanished in 2-3 hours. The solid was, however, much more stable. Examined after an hour the specific rotation of the solid was found to be $+50^\circ$ and when kept cool and examined after three hours, the specific rotation fell to $+20.5^\circ$, the actual rotations being $+1.0^\circ$ and $+0.41^\circ$ respectively with a 1% solution. Examined after 6 hours the salt was found to be quite inactive.

d-Triethylenediaminozinc sulphate was prepared in the same way as the chloride by decomposing the *d-triethylenediaminozinc-camphor nitronate* with dilute sulphuric acid and precipitation with acetone. [Found: N, 24.75; Zn, 19.10; SO_4 , 28.56. $(\text{ZnEn}_3)\text{SO}_4$ requires

N, 24.63 ; Zn, 19.06 ; SO₄, 28.14 per cent.]. Rotation of the substance was determined in a 2 dcm. tube with a solution of the concentration (0.513 g. in 15 c.c.) when the rotation was found to be +0.6° which makes $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +87.7^\circ$ and $[M] = 299.08^\circ$. The solution when examined after three hours was found to be quite inactive whereas the solid when kept cool and examined after 3 hours showed its specific rotation to be +15.2°, the value of α_D being +0.76° with a 25% solution but when examined after 6 hours was found to be quite inactive.

Triethylenediaminozinc camphornitronate.—A solution of triethylenediaminozinc chloride (5 g.) in water (15 c.c.) was triturated with moist silver oxide. The solution of the complex hydroxide was filtered and the residue washed with water and to the clear alkaline filtrate thus obtained nitrocamphor was gradually added (6 g. in all) with constant stirring whereby all the nitrocamphor almost dissolved. The solution was then filtered and evaporated in vacuum when a tarry mass containing some crystalline substance was obtained which on repeated crystallisation was separated from the tarry matter. The substance was then fractionally crystallised. The first fraction was found to have a specific rotation of -42.6° the actual rotation being -2.56° with a 3% of solution examined in a 2 dcm. tube. The rotation of this substance also did not change on keeping. It was found to have identical chemical composition with that of the *dextro* variety.

1. *Triethylenediaminozinc chloride in solution*.—The *laevo*-triethylenediaminozinc camphor nitronate crystals (1 g.) were dissolved in water (15 c.c) and dilute hydrochloric acid was added drop by drop when nitrocamphor was found to precipitate out which was filtered off. The rotation of the solution was observed in a 2 dcm. tube when it was found to be -1.16° but it completely racemised in an hour and a half. On adding acetone in excess no precipitate of the active substance could be obtained. The preparation of other salts is in progress.

